

Polarographic Studies on the Complexes Formed by Cd(II) with Furylamine and 2-Amino Pyrimidine in Aqueous Formamide Mixtures

S. K. BHASIN*, OM PARKASH*, D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR

Chemical laboratory, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur

Manuscript received 23 September 1977, revised 18 July 1978, accepted 22 December 1978

The composition and stability constants of the complexes formed by Cd(II) with furylamine and 2-amino pyrimidine in aqueous formamide mixtures have been determined polarographically. In case of furylamine, three complex species with $\log \beta_1 = 2.000$, $\log \beta_2 = 2.954$, and $\log \beta_3 = 4.243$ in 25% formamide and $\log \beta_1 = 2.301$, $\log \beta_2 = 3.380$, and $\log \beta_3 = 4.607$ in 75% formamide were formed. 2-Amino pyrimidine forms only two complexes in 20, 40 and 60% formamide mixtures and these complexes are much weaker as compared to that of furylamine complexes. The stability of furylamine complexes with Cd(II) is found to increase with increase in the percentage of formamide. Although the stability of Cd(II)-2, amino pyrimidine complexes is lesser in aqueous formamide mixtures than in aqueous medium, it is not affected much with increase in the percentage of formamide.

CADMIUM complexes in non-aqueous media have been studied polarographically primarily by Khot'syanovaskii and Kundera¹⁻² and by Migal and his co-workers³⁻⁵. Further studies on the complexes of Cd(II) with a number of ligands in different aqueous organic solvent mixtures have been carried out extensively by Gaur and co-workers⁶⁻¹⁵. However, the complexes formed by furylamine and 2-amino pyrimidine with metal ions have not been studied so far. It was observed that Cd(II) forms insoluble complexes with furylamine which solubilise by the addition of formamide. Cd(II)-2 amino pyrimidine complex were soluble in aqueous medium, but to compare the effect of formamide as a solvent on complexes formation with change in the nature of ligand, the investigations were carried out in the presence of formamide. The present paper describes the polarographic determination of composition and formation constants of the complexes formed by Cd(II) with furylamine in 25% and 75% formamide and with 2-amino pyrimidine in 20%, 40% and 50% formamide.

Experimental

A manual polarograph was used for taking the polarograms. Capillary characteristics for the open circuit were: $m = 1.76$ m.gm/sec. and $t = 3.64$ sec. A constant temperature of $30 \pm 0.01^\circ$ was maintained by means of a Haake type ultra thermostat. Purified nitrogen was used for removing oxygen from solutions through a pre-saturator of the same solvent composition. The ionic strength of the solutions were maintained at 0.1 by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate. A conventional H-type cell

with an agar-agar plug saturated with NaCl was used for all the measurements. The half-wave potentials reported are corrected for IR drop.

Results and Discussion

In each case, a single well defined diffusion controlled wave appeared. The plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ were found to be linear with a slope of 32 ± 1.0 mv, showing the reversibility of the reduction ($n=2$). The half-wave potential shifted towards more negative value and the diffusion current was found to decrease with increase in ligand concentration which indicated complex formation.

Cd(II)-Furylamine System :

Solutions containing 0.5 mM Cadmium and different concentrations of the ligand (0.05 to 0.40M) were prepared in 25% and 75% formamide by volume.

DeFord and Hume's¹⁶ method modified by Irving¹⁷ was applied to determine formation constants. The overall formation constants calculated from $F_1([X])$ vs C_x plots in different concentrations of formamide are given below :

Percentage of formamide (by volume)	Stability constants		
	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$
25	2.00	2.95	4.24
75	2.30	3.38	4.61

* Present Address : M. L. N. College, Yamna Nagar (Haryana).

It is clear that furylamine forms three complexes with Cd(II) having the composition [Cd(furylamine)]²⁺, [Cd(furylamine)₂]²⁺ and [Cd(furylamine)₃]²⁺ in both the concentrations of formamide. The stability of these complexes increases with increase in the concentration of formamide in the solvent.

The plots of F_j([X]) vs C_x in 75% formamide are presented in Fig. 1. The polarographic

Fig. 1. Plots of F_j([X]) vs C_x in 75% formamide.

characteristics and F₀([X]) functions for the system in 25% and 75% formamide have been summarised in Table 1. The percentage distribution of Cd(II)

Fig. 2. % distribution of various Complexes species in 25% formamide (————) & 75% formamide (-----).

Cd(II)-2, Amino Pyrimidine System :

Solutions containing 0.5 mM Cd(II) and different concentrations of 2-amino pyrimidine (0.10M to 0.80M) were prepared in 20%, 40% and 60% by volume of formamide.

On extrapolation of F_j([X]) values to zero ligand concentrations the overall stability constants in

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F₀([X]) VALUES OF Cd(II)-FURYLAMINE SYSTEM IN AQUEOUS FORMAMIDE MIXTURES

C _x (Moles)	25% Formamide			75% Formamide		
	-E _{1/2} (V vs SCE)	i _d (Divs.)	F ₀ ([X])	-E _{1/2} (V vs SCE)	i _d (Divs)	F ₀ ([X])
0.00	0.602	65.0	—	0.625	49.0	—
0.10	0.650	63.0	42.7	0.679	46.5	74.6
0.15	0.661	62.0	97.1	0.694	45.5	223.2
0.20	0.670	61.0	196.9	0.704	45.5	462.9
0.25	0.677	60.5	353.0	0.712	45.0	832.6
0.30	0.684	59.5	591.2	0.718	45.0	1371.0
0.35	0.689	58.5	916.8	0.723	45.0	2090.0
0.40	0.694	58.5	1346.0	0.728	44.5	2980.0

present in various forms as a logarithm of furylamine concentration in 25% and 75% formamide solutions has been presented in Fig. 2.

various concentrations of formamide were calculated and presented below. The complexes of Cd(II) with 2-amino pyrimidine in the aqueous medium

have also been studied by the authors¹⁸ and included for comparison.

Percentage of formamide (by volume)	Stability Constants	
	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$
0	1.70	1.03
20	1.74	0.38
40	1.70	0.38
60	1.65	0.48

It shows the presence of only two complex species with the composition $[Cd(2 \text{ A.P.})]^{2+}$ and $[Cd(2 \text{ A.P.})_2]^{2+}$ in all cases. Although the composition of complexes is not affected, the stability of the second complex is decreased appreciably in the presence of formamide, and the stability of the complexes is not affected much as the percentage of formamide is increased from 20 to 60.

The plots of $F_j([X])$ values vs C_x in 60% formamide are presented in Fig. 3. The polarographic

Fig. 3. --- Plots of $F_j([X])$ vs C_x in 60% formamide.

in 20%, 40% and 60% formamide are given in Table 2. The percentage distribution of Cd(II) present in various forms as a logarithm of 2-amino pyrimidine concentration in 20% and 60% formamide solution has been presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. composition in 20% formamide (—) & 60% formamide (---)

characteristics and $F_0([X])$ values for the systems

The results show that the stability of Cd(II) complexes with furylamine is affected more as compared with that of 2-amino pyrimidine (comparatively weaker ligand) in the presence of formamide.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_0([X])$ FUNCTIONS FOR Cd(II)-2 AMINO PYRIMIDINE SYSTEM IN AQUEOUS FORMAMIDE MIXTURES

C_x (Moles)	20% Formamide			40% Formamide			60% Formamide		
	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (V vs SCE)	i_d (Divs)	$F_0([X])$	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (V vs SCE)	i_d (Divs)	$F_0([X])$	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (V vs SCE)	i_d (Divs)	$F_0([X])$
0.00	0.595	67.0	—	0.601	61.0	—	0.604	56.5	—
0.10	0.596	66.5	1.09	0.601	59.0	1.07	0.607	56.5	1.00
0.20	0.597	62.5	1.20	0.603	58.0	1.23	0.608	55.5	1.33
0.30	0.599	62.5	1.40	0.604	56.5	1.36	0.609	53.5	1.43
0.40	0.600	59.5	1.62	0.606	56.5	1.58	0.610	53.5	1.67
0.50	0.601	58.5	1.78	0.607	54.0	1.86	0.612	52.5	1.99
0.60	0.603	57.5	2.19	0.609	52.5	2.15	0.614	45.5	2.41
0.70	0.605	57.0	2.58	0.610	52.5	2.32	0.616	47.5	2.99
0.80	0.608	57.0	3.07	0.613	51.5	2.97	0.619	47.5	3.62

References

1. C. I. KHOTSYANOVSKII and O. K. KUNDRA, *Chem., Abs.*, 1958, **54**, 196081.
2. C. I. KHOTSYANOVSKII and O. K. KUNDRA, *Khim i Khim Tekhnol.*, 1958, **1**, 43.
3. P. K. MIGAL and A. N. PUSHNYAK, *Russian J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1960, **5**, 293.
4. P. K. MIGAL and N. GRINBERG, *Russian J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1961, **6**, 369.
5. P. K. MIGAL and G. P. SAROVA, *Russian J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **7**, 827.
6. J. N. GAUR and V. K. SHARMA, *Rev. Polarog. Soc. Japan*, 1967, **14**, 287.
7. J. N. GAUR and V. K. SHARMA, *Acta Chimica (Hungary)*, 1968, **55**, 249.
8. M. M. PALRECHA, Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1969.
9. ANAND KUMAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1972.
10. J. N. GAUR, D. S. JAIN and P. S. VERMA, *J. Electrochem. Soc. of India*, 1974, **22-4**, 213.
11. A. K. MAHESHWARI, D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *Bull. DE.L' Academie*, 1975, **22**, (No. 11), 987.
12. K. K. CHOUDHRY, D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *J. Electrochem. Society of India*, 1976, **25**.
13. S. C. BAGHEL, Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1975.
14. OM DUTT, Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1975.
15. D. S. JAIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (In press).
16. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321.
17. H. IRVING, *Advances in Polarography*, Ed. I.S., Longmuir, Pergamon Press, London (1960) Vol. I. p. 42.
18. S. K. BHASIN, Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur (India), 1977.